

HISTORICAL PLACES OF ASIA AND THEIR ROLE TO TOURISM

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Abstract. *Asia’s ancient landmarks and their significance to Tourism and these places are not only admired to their beauty and extraordinary construction but also for the stories, deep meanings they carry across time. Asia, the largest and most diverse continent on the Earth, is a treasure trove of ancient civilizations, spiritual heritage, and timeless architectural wonders.*

Key words: *Asia, the Nabatiens, landmarks, rainwater harvesting, Mughal Emperor Shah Jahan, Mumtaz Mahal, tourist attractions, tourism industry, China, Petra, historical.*

According to New7Wonders (2007), all three landmarks—the Great Wall of China, the TajMahal, and Petra—were named among the New Seven Wonders of the World due to their architectural brilliance and global cultural impact. Today, they attract millions of tourists, playing a crucial role learning our history that who were our ancestors and what they were capable to do around 2300-2700 years ago. Also they carry hidden secrets and traditions during the decades which is influenced by ancient people. In our modern life they play significant role and reason why I choose these landmarks there are incredible and magical places. This paper explores The Great Wall of China as a symbol of national security and unity, Taj Mahal as an enduring monument of love and Petra as a remarkable place of old trade, architecture and engineering. Moreover, these places are contributing to both economic growth and an increase of number of tourists.

Historical Background

The historical and cultural heritage plays crucial role in development of Tourism. Each of the three landmarks- The Great Wall of China, the Taj Mahal, and Petra- has unique ancient background that reflects the civilization it came from. Built as early as the 7th century BCE, with major reconstruction during the Ming Dynasty (1368–1644) to protect China’s northern borders and its incredible length and defensive architecture shows the military priorities and organizational capabilities of China at that time. Total length of it more than 20,000 kilometers and the height of it 6.6 meters (in some parts 8-10 meters). In every 100 meters there is rectangular tower (height 10-12 meters) for guards to report about situation. 2.500 years spent to built it fully. It’s literal meaning “The long wall” (wan li chang cheng) and this wall is 2,700 years old. In Alisher Navoi's epic poem "Saddi Iskandariy"(1485), the Great Wall of China is mentioned as the "Saddi Chin" wall. According to history, ordinary people especially, man from each family forced to join the building and even if they died while working , it was very likely to bury their dead bodies under or near The Great Wall. Due to the heavy work, the guardians would not like to spend time to send dead bodies away for burial. From this we can understand how difficult it was at that time working at the building and we can get information about their religion. To sum up, it was nothing common peoples’ life worth. Between 1960-1980 years the Wall destroyed to built farms and civilian houses and some people even despoiled the stones and sold them. Majority of people consider that, The Great Wall one of the only man-made building that observable from space but that is a lie .

Because the wall closely resembles the surrounding stone and soil, it's even difficult to distinguish it with the human eye from a low altitude. Actually, Great Wall of China is most notorious structures in the entire world but it couldn't help defend The Empire, for example, throughout history, enemies often found weak or vulnerable sections of the wall or simply bypassed it. The wall was not continuous knowing that reason invaders would often search ways around it. Especially, Mongols in 13th century, Kublai Khan in 1271 and the Manchus crossed the Wall and established The Qing Dynasty in 1644.

Petra

The world's one of the New7Wonders is Red rock –cut capital city Petra was built in 4th century BCE by the

Nabateans, it's also called “Rose City”. At that time this city was the trade center for Arabia, Egypt was carved directly into it a sandstone cliff. “You will see a living city in front of you,” says Al- Salameen (2018), a native of the area who spent his youth exploring among Petra's temples, monuments and houses. This city consists of temple architecture and vast extent of elaborate tomb, religious high places, churches, remnant channels, tunnels diversion dams that reached with a huge connections of cisterns and reservoirs which controlled and conserved seasonal rains. However, in Byzantine era there were built many Christian churches but city already had been started losing its importance year by year. The main reasons were earthquakes and appearance of sea routes for trade. Before earthquakes damaged the city Petra's population was around 30,000 people, but in A.D 363 city lost many buildings following the another damage centuries later residents of city decreased extremely. This city was left unknown to western countries but in 1812 traveler Johann Ludwig who is from Switzerland uncovered once more it to the world.

Taj Mahal

Taj Mahal is located in the Agra district right bank of the Yamuna River in vast Mughal garden totally 17 hectares and it was built by Mughal Emperor Shah Jahan in memory of his wife queen Mumtaz Mahal. The building structure started in 1632 AD and finished in 1648 AD including the guest house, mosque, main gateway on the south, the outer courtyard and its cloisters were added and completed in 1653 AD. For its construction, masons, stone –cutters, inlayers, carvers, painters, calligraphers, builders, artists were requested from the whole the whole Empire and also from Central Asia and Iran. The main architect of the Taj Mahal was Ustad - Ahmad Lahori. It is the greatest work of Indo –Islamic architecture. Its design is admired for the balanced interplay of solid and empty spaces, the harmony of curved and straight lines, and the contrast of light and shadow. Features like arches and domes enhance its visual appeal. The striking mix of red stone pathways, lush green gardens, and the blue sky above all highlight the monument's charm, which changes subtly with the light. Intricate marble relief work and detailed inlays using precious and semi-precious stones make the Taj Mahal truly unique. What sets the Taj Mahal apart are several extraordinary ideas introduced by the horticulturists and architects serving under Shah Jahan. One such innovation was placing the tomb not at the exact center of the four-part garden, but at one end, giving it a greater sense of depth and enhancing the view. The monument is also a notable example of a raised tomb structure. The building's layout is highly symmetrical, with an octagonal central tomb room surrounded by four smaller rooms and entry halls. This layout is mirrored on the floor above. From the outside, the tomb appears square with its corners chamfered. At its heart lies a double-story octagonal chamber that contains the cenotaphs of Mumtaz Mahal and Shah Jahan.

Symbolic and Cultural Significance

Beyond their physical beauty, these landmarks carry deep symbolic meanings tied to their national and cultural identities. The Great Wall represents strength, perseverance and determination of Chinese citizens. Here is an Chinese proverb as well: “Who has not climbed to the Great Wall is not true man” (Mao, Z, 1935, Traditional Chinese proverbs) that shows it is an emblem of national pride and one of the greatest architectural achievements of China. “The Great Wall is not only a proud symbol of our civilization but also a driver of cultural tourism and rural revitalization” (President of China, Xi J. 2024). In addition, in 1987 Wall identified as a UNESCO World Heritage Site, it reflects the value of the Wall in the international level. Taj Mahal is a symbol of infinite love and emphasizes the great respect to the woman in islam. Every year millions of lovers go to this landmark and take picture at the entrance, it is some kind of international beautiful tradition. In 1992 Prince Charles and Princess Diana went to India with official purpose unfortunately princess went to Taj Mahal and took a picture alone because years ago prince visited there alone as well and informed to everyone: “Next time I will come with my lover”. After that sad event, 2 month later they divorced. It is also cultural icon of India and represents the wealthy history, architecture of that times. In the interior plan of Taj there is 8 level of principle which is called “hasht bishisht” and means the 8 levels of paradise. Petra – emblem of creativity and architectural brilliance of the Nabataean civilization. During the years it is still represents the hidden wonders of historical magic world. No matter how many thousands of years past city’s water harvesting system is still wonderful discovery and exploring by scientists till now. In every step of learning they are showing us how genius were ancient civilization and people.

Impact on Economy and Tourism

Nowadays, all of this places have crucial impact on their countries economy and tourism. Every year millions of tourists are coming to exploring this sites and this is boosting the economy of these countries . Generates high tourism revenue for India and creates jobs in the hospitality sector that is also helping to increase people’s life balance. Because India is the richest and at the same time the poorest country in the world. Preservation efforts are also economically significant. China is in the second place on earning money from tourism with the help of The Great Wall and this country is making \$2.1.billion a year. Petra is the most visited city in Jordan and from entrance fees, guided tours, hospitality services (hotels, restaurants, transport) with that this landmark is also improving the tourism and economy. Creating thousands of job offers to the people . Petra is located in desert surrounding villages benefit from economic activity because it is helping to education, improved infrastructures and services. Moreover, they are bringing global fame this countries.

This diagram illustrates the number of travelers that visited to The Great Wall of China, ‘rose city’ Petra, Taj Mahal from the whole world during the 2016, 2019 and 2023. It’s clear that in 2016 The Great Wall had highest results (11.5 million) and Petra had lowest (465,096) because during that years there were so many wars in Syria and Iraq the bordering countries to the Jordan . That’s why people were afraid of coming to Petra and another reasons: less advertising, location hard to go and that times there were not developed too much for tourist visiting . Taj Mahal got second place with 6.2 million travelers. In 2019, Great Wall had the highest figure still but decreased to 1.5 million because of COVID-19 and landmark closed officially for quarantine in January 2020. Taj Mahal were closed because of pandemic between 2021-2022 and experienced with slightly decrease in 2023 year for 1.5 million. Only Petra and The Great Wall of China can revived again. Overall, according to the statistics, Petra is developing new tourist attraction that is why it has lower tourist footstep and income than another 2 landmarks for now and I should mention that Petra officially opened to tourists in 1960-1970 years.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Petra, the Great Wall of China, and the Taj Mahal are not only architectural marvels but also significant drivers of tourism, contributing to the economies and cultural identities of their countries. Each of these sites offers a unique glimpse into history and continues to captivate visitors worldwide, proving that preserving such landmarks is essential for both cultural heritage and economic growth. As a Asian person I proud of living here and having opportunity to see such kind of masterpieces. World unities are also trying to save them to the new generations as well because they should know that they had such kind of great ancestors who able to built this landmarks without any new technology.

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